

Climate Change Impact on Faunal Diversity

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Abstract:

The environmental factors are active in the surrounding like sunlight, wind, precipitation and humidity are dynamic factors in the weather. these factors affect the environment on the earth as well as all living thing, since the creation of the earth there have been continuous processes in earth atmosphere and weather. by observing the continuous changes in the climatic elements. the element which can provide the need of man and they use of large scale.

Environmental issues are a growing concern in today's world all the countries including India are facing excessive environmental issues. Climate change has a significant impact on forest increased in deforestation in causing change in the land surface the fuels contribution Loss of biodiversity increase in the carbon dioxide in large quantities. the increasing industrialization in the country has an adverse impact on the climate forests should be the largest part of the land mass on earth but only 23% of the land area is forested which affects wildlife diversity the temperature is increasing day by day which is called global warming the average temperature on land and sea surface has increased by 19 degrees Celsius due to climate change,

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Introduction:

Climate change refers to long term shifts in temperatures and weather patterns. Climate change affects everyone, but the most vulnerable population, who have contributed the least to the problem are often the hardest hit. Addressing climate change is crucial for protecting our environment, health, and future generation. Cutting down forests reduces the number of trees that can absorb carbon dioxide, increasing the amount of this greenhouse gas in the atmosphere. Certain industrial activities release greenhouse gases, including methane and nitrous oxide, which contribute to global warming. Factors that increase the temperature of the earth industry and transportation cause air pollution.

The earth average surface temperature has increased, leading to more frequent and

severe heat waves. Increased temperature contributes to more intense and unpredictable weather pattern, including hurricanes, floods, and drought. Melting ice cap and glaciers, along with the thermal expansion of sea water, are causing sea level to rise, threatening coastal communities. Many species are struggling to adapt to the rapid changes in their habitats, leading to a decline in biodiversity. Climate change can exacerbate health issues, such as respiratory problem due to which increase the temperature of the earth this is called the greenhouse effect a significant and long-term change in the pattern of rainfall, wind systems and temperature this is called climate change. the situation is the becoming more serious due to the increasing population and the increasing use of the modern polluting. Technology the result of this is that global

warming rate of melting of ice at the polar the continuous rise in the water level of the ocean which is not stopped. in the time but there is a fear of the country going underwater. the main result of climate change is that South Asian countries like India are dependent on the rainfall that Falls. at certain time for drinking and irrigation however due to the increase in the temperature this rainy season is going to forward by the least 18 to 15 days. due to the global warming increasing carbon dioxide in the of the ocean water in the increasing which will result in the extension of the life in the ocean and intern decline of the ecosystem if you went to prevent this you have to start with yourself right.

You can a definitely, do this why limiting the use of plastic recycling and using natural resources, wisely our generation is the first to experience the consequence of climate change and the last to do something about it the major global issue. today the world is the becoming more vulnerable to climate change. climate change describes changes in the earth climate. over a period of decades to year the average Global temperature could rise by 6 degrees Celsius by the end of the century. according to the United National metrological recent report has expressed that climate change had a profound impact on the environment and ecosystems. the earth climate is changing the you holding most of changing and you most of the change natural phenomena. like volcano eruption floods, forest fire etc., some of the fires caused by human activities deforestation burning of fossil fuels livestock agriculture etc. The causes a large amount of greenhouse effect and global warming. which are the main causes of climate change. if the current situation of the climate change continuous it will have a huge impact on all homes of light on the animals. will rise and the earth temperature increase and the natural disaster will occur more frequently. the earth ecological

balance will be distributed the environment will be polluted and the human will not get fresh air.

To breathe and clean water drinking the earth will end step should be taken to reduce climate change. the government of India has taken caller majors to improve the solution of the climate change. the ministry of the Environment and Forest is the nodal agency for especially in the field of climate change issues in India. it has taken many renewal energy. India has taken cellar policies majors awareness about the climate change and build capacity for addictive measures for this green. India program has been launched its forest land is the greener and the more fertile measurement can be taken to address the issue of climate change. to effectively address the issue of the climate change we must adopt the path of sustainable development. we must reduce the use of wholesale view which is the main causes of global warming to make a progressive trances vacation to clean energy. we must adobe alternative source of energy. such as hydroelectric, geothermal, solar, wind energy etc. increased air pollution, and the spread of diseases as warmer temperatures expand the range of disease carrying insects.

There are various factors responsible for climate change. These climate changes create adverse environmental impact on man and environment. It is very important to study the climate change in detail the understanding climate change has evolved significantly over the countries with key milestones the progress of scientific knowledge. climate change shift ecosystems forcing species to move to new habitats disrupting ecological interaction and causing imbalances. climate change refers to long term shift in temperature and weather patterns human activities have been the main driver of climate change. primarily due to burning of fossil fuels like coal, oil and gas.

Related factor involves in climate change:

In the last 18 century after the invention of the engine, industrialization began worldwide due to the large-scale use of coal for power generation a huge amount of carbon dioxide and methane was released in to the atmosphere and due to these gases. the solar radiation reflected from the earth remaining in the earth s atmosphere which increased the temperature of the earth.

Effect of climate change:

climate change has created many challenges like imbalance in rainfall pattern on the earth increase in the temperature melting of the Glacier rise in sea level increase in disasters, outbreak of disease increasing incidence of skin disease adverse effect on living organism if we study different gases in the atmosphere, we realise that the level of carbon dioxide gas is continuously increase day by day.

Change in the Seasons:

Summer and winter are the considered, to be the two main season in the world, however due to recent climate change the duration of Summer is increasing while the duration of winter is decreasing.

Decrease in snow covered:

Areas due to increase in the summer duration the rate of melting of snow is increasing due to this the area covered by snow is decreasing and Glacier are retreating due to the melting of snow the land is exposed and the amount of heat absorb by the land has increased due to these the temperature in the snow-covered area is increasing.

Impact on Rainfall:

Climate change has major impact on rainfall the uncertainly a rainfall has increased the

some places heavy rainfall leads to floods and wet droughts in other place droughts occur due to sudden decrease in rainfall.

Effect on winds:

Climate change causes a sudden increase in the temperature in some place and decrease in temperature in order due to the decrease in air pressure in the place where the temperature has increased the wind start blowing faster from the surrounding areas of high air pressure of cyclone the amount of rainfall decrease in the place, where the winds are blowing in the areas of high air pressure.

Impact on water resources:

All living things on earth need food and water to survive climate change has and adverse impact on water resources if the variability of rainfall, in region increase it become harmful to living things the impact of rainfall is seen to have an adverse impact on the industries, agriculture, health etc.

- **Health impact on the forest wealth:** Along the temperature water is the required for plant growth both temperature and water supply due to climate change it will affect forest wealth different type of forest is formed depending on temperature and water availability however due to climate change the type of forest is all, changing due to lack of water and rising temperature forest in some places have disappeared and the process of desertification as begun.
- **Impact on human health:** Any change in climate has and adverse impact on human health this change in climate, effects children and elderly more because children and the elderly do not have the mains to adopt to the changing climate as a result they have to face health problem.

Some measures to Control Climate Change:

Climate change is creating many serious problems, and we are facing various challenges. It is necessary to control climate change for the survival of human and ecosystem. For these, if some measures are taken, the following are the measures that will control climate change.

1. To promote the tree conservation movement by controlling deforestation.
2. Effort to reduce the amount of carbon dioxide gas in the atmosphere.
3. Prevent all types of pollution.
4. Conserving all types of resources.
5. To control industrialisation, urbanisation and population growth.
6. Increase the use of vehicles powered by non-conventional energy.
7. Strengthen implementation of environmental laws by reducing increasing interference in the environment.
8. Everyone should take care that greenhouse gases do not enter the atmosphere.
8. Development of renewable energy sources and generation of polluting-free energy.
9. To plan and implement an action program along with public education and awareness regarding climate change.
10. Building on environmental momentum through a parallel system that provides information and climate change.

Impact of climate change on wide a life diversity

- **Habitat loss:** The temperature variation in climate change is having a serious impact on wildlife and biodiversity. Many species are on the way to extinction due to habitat loss, rising temperatures, droughts, floods, and melting snow. This causes animals to currently struggle for food. This is causing a change in the deer migration pattern, leading to increased human-wildlife conflict. Habitat loss and

global warming have destroyed the natural habitats of the polar bear, penguin, and many other species in the Western Ghats.

- **Trust of species extension:** Nearly half of the world's wild animals' ranges are at high risk of extinction, especially in sensitive areas like the Amazon and Galapagos.
- **Disruption to the food chain:** Climate change is causing plants to flower and fruit earlier, which is affecting plants that eat the seeds and animals.
- **Migrations and reproduction:** Many marine animals are migrating toward the coastal region, which coral reefs are being destroyed due to marine heat waves.
- **Human-wildlife conflict:** Animals are entering urban settlements due to the lack of food, causing wildlife to be shrinking. Also, in India, about 3% of birds and animals are on the way to extinction due to climate change, while 19% of amphibians' ranges are critically endangered. The impact on biodiversity hotspots is beginning to be felt. To prevent this change, it is necessary to reduce carbon emissions and protect natural habitats.

Conclusion:

Today, environmental issues are growing. Many climatic elements are changing and exploding. Pollutant factors, climate change, and a large scale of degradation in the ecosystem are causing many environmental problems to be faced by humans. If we stop the changes in the environment, issues to aware human-bangung, climate change current contribution to human-wildlife conflict is to be period, it so only then can wildlife be protected if climate change is the stop, otherwise it will take for many a line spaces become extinct.

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